

ARCHAEOLOGICAL STUDY OF BRONZE AGE SETTLEMENTS IN THE AKCHADARYA BASIN AND THE LOWER ZARAFSHAN VALLEY

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Annotasiya. Maqolada Quyi Amudaryo va Zarafshon va g'arbiy hududlarida bronza davri so'g'd manzilgohlarni arxeologik izlanishlar natijalari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar. Vinogradov A.V, Tolstov S.P, Itina M.A, Askarov A, Oqchadaryo, Quyi Zarafshon, Sho'raxon, Qizilqum Qoraqum, Angqa-5, Qavat-3, Jonbas - 33, Ko'kcha -15,16. Ko'kcha-3, Zamonbobo, Sulton Sanjar, Qo'shbuloq, Qarriqizil, Mo'minobod.

Аннотация. В статье анализирован результаты археологических исследования поселения бронзового периода на территории Западного Согда и Низовья Амударьи.

Ключевые слова. Виноградов А.В, Толстов С.П, Итина М.А, Аскарлов А, Акчадарье, Низовья Зеравшан, Шурахон, Кызылкум, Каракум Ангка-5, Заман-Баба, Султон Санжар, Кушбулак, Каррыкызил, Муминабад.

Abstract. The article analyzes the results of archaeological research on Bronze Age Sogdian settlements in the lower Amu Darya and Zeravshan regions.

Key words. Vinogradov A.V., Tolstov S.P., Itina M.A., Askarov A., Akchadarya, Lower Zeravshan, Shurahon, Kyzylkum, Karakum Angka-5, Zaman-Baba, Sulton Sanzhar, Kushbulak, Karrykyzil, Muminabad.

Kirish. (Введение / Introduction)

The article discusses the archaeological study of Bronze Age settlements in the Akchadarya basin and the lower region of the Zeravshan River as a result of geological processes. It is known from archaeological literature that the study of settlements from the Bronze Age has been conducted synchronously since the mid-20th century. The Amudarya River, due to its main flow towards the northern plains, is divided into lowland left and right areas between the Kyzylkum and Karakum deserts, with their geographical landscapes not repeating each other. The rising water level of the Amudarya, particularly from the northern region of the Shorakhon village towards the Kyzylkum plays a significant role in the formation of the Akchadarya basin. The geographical position of the right bank of the Amudarya continues to be explained by the activities of the Zeravshan River.

In this sense, the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zeravshan valley form a unified geographical region between the Amudarya and the Syrdarya. These areas were formed due to the sedimentation of muddy layers, which have contained mineral substances in the river water over thousands of years, providing favourable conditions for human habitation and agriculture. This

article aims to highlight how our ancestors utilized the fertile areas in their daily practical activities.

In the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zarafshan Valley, archaeological reconnaissance work was carried out by the Khorezm Expedition and the Archaeological Group of the Archaeology Department of the Institute of History and Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As part of these efforts, traces of human cultural activity were registered, and labor tools explaining these traces were collected. Brief historical information about these findings was recorded in publications.

The Khorezm Expedition staff extensively studied the economic activities of Neolithic tribal communities in the Akchadarya basin, as reflected in A.V. Vinogradov's early monograph on the Jonbos-4 site. This work examined the economic adaptation and settlement results of tribal communities in the Akchadarya, providing valuable academic sources¹. In his subsequent study, the researcher documented sources related to the economic and cultural history of the populations settled between the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers. This included materials shedding light on ethnic processes in the Akchadarya basin, the Lower Zarafshan Valley, the interior of the Kyzylkum Desert, and the lower Syr Darya basin². According to archaeological literature, the study of Bronze Age sites in the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zarafshan region began in the mid-1950s. M.A. Itina, a student of S.P. Tolstov, conducted initial excavations in the southern Akchadarya basin, specifically in the Turtkul and Beruni regions (modern-day Ellikqala district), leading to the discovery of archaeological sites. Excavations at sites such as Angqa-5, Qavat-3, and Kkcha-3 provided material evidence illuminating the socio-economic and ethno-cultural interactions of the Bronze Age. Notably, during the cleaning of burials at the Kkcha-3 site, skeletal remains were found, offering unique insights into the religious beliefs of the local population³. During the 1970s and 1980s, further excavations in the Akchadarya basin and Tuyamuyin regions uncovered new material evidence related to Bronze Age settlements. Investigations at Jonbos and Kkcha sites identified several settlements, including Jonbos 33 and 34, as well as Kkcha 15,

¹**Vinogradov, A.V.** *Neolithic Monuments of Khorezm*. Moscow: Nauka, 1968. Issue 8, 170 pages.

²**Vinogradov, A.V.** "Ancient Hunters and Fishermen of the Central Asian Interfluvium" // *Transactions of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition*. Moscow: Nauka, 1981. Issue XIII, 160 pages.

³**Tolstov, S.P.** "Works of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition in 1954" // *Soviet Oriental Studies*. Moscow, 1955. No. 6, pp. 99-103. **Itina, M.A.** "New Sites of the Tazabagyab Culture (Works of 1956)" // *Materials of the Khorezm Expedition*. Moscow: Nauka, 1959. Issue I, pp. 52-150. **Itina, M.A.** "Excavations of the Kavats-3 Site in 1958" // *Materials of the Khorezm Expedition*. Moscow: Nauka, 1963. Issue 6, pp. 103-106. **Itina, M.A.** "Excavations of the Tazabagyab Culture Site in 1957" // *Materials of the Khorezm Expedition*. Moscow: Nauka, 1960. No. 6, pp. 99-103. **Itina, M.A.** "Excavations of the Tazabagyab Culture Burial Ground Kkcha-3" // *Materials of the Khorezm Expedition*. Moscow, 1961. Issue 5, pp. 3-96.

16, 21, and 22. Similarly, in Tuyamuyin, cultural layers at Sultan Sanjar, Qarriqizil, and Qoshbulov sites revealed human cultural traces⁴.

Bronze Age settlements in the Lower Zarafshan region were explored under the leadership of Ya.G. Gulomov and the Mahondarya Archaeology Group. Research focused on settlements built on the shores of a dried-up lake, where ancient inhabitants constructed wooden-post dwellings. These early settlers practiced agriculture on fertile lands, and skeletal remains from cemeteries provided insights into ethnic processes⁵. Additionally, in the mountainous areas of the Central Zarafshan region, burials containing anthropological materials were discovered, highlighting the development of economic and cultural practices among communities in both the plains and foothills⁶. It is important to note that in the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zarafshan Valley, the descendants of Neolithic tribal communities adapted to the changing conditions of the Amu Darya and Zarafshan rivers. By effectively utilizing natural resources, they pioneered agricultural practices, laying the foundation for the development of production-based economies, as confirmed by the archaeological findings.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi [Research Methodology].

Scientific objectivity, theoretical-comparative analysis, substantiation, generalization, logical conclusions, and advancements in the fields of archaeology, geography, and ethnography were utilized.

(Результаты / Results)

The results of archaeological investigations conducted by the Khorezm Expedition and the Mahondaryo archaeological group between the Shorakhon and Sul-ton Uvays mountains and in the lower Zarafshon basin have been analysed.

(Заключение / Conclusion)

It was noted that the Bronze Age population underwent ethnic processes in the region formed by the geographical landscape joining the Kzylkum desert

⁴ **Itina, M.A.** "Excavations on the Akchadarya" // *Archaeological Discoveries 1976*. Moscow: Nauka, 1977, p. 527. **Itina, M.A.** "Monuments of the Neolithic and Bronze Ages" // *Antiquities of Southern Khorezm // Transactions of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition*. Moscow: Nauka, Volume XVI, pp. 72-79.

⁵ **Askarov, A.** "The Zaman-Baba Culture in the Lower Zeravshan" // *News of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR*. Tashkent: Fan, 1962. No. 1, pp. 59-65. **Askarov, A.** *Scenes from the Primitive History of Bukhara*. Tashkent: Fan, 1973, pp. 15-21.

⁶ **Askarov, A.** "Excavations of the Bronze Age Burial Ground in Muminabad" // *Materials of the Khorezm Expedition*. Tashkent: Fan, 1969. Issue 8, pp. 56-62.

south of the Shorakhon village in archaeological literature regarding the right bank of the Amudarya and the Lower Zarafshon valley.

It was concluded that the area of the Akchadarya basin and the southern region was the site of daily activities by the Bronze Age population.

The Bronze Age inhabitants of the Akchadarya basin densely populated the area around the Shorakhon village and the Sulton Uvays mountains, engaging in practical activities in the geographical region. It was concluded that daily activities of the population in the Lower Zarafshon valley occurred around large and small watercourses.

The following suggestions were made:

The necessity of studying the history of daily activities of the population in the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zarafshon valley, who effectively utilized water resources.

Attention should be given to the interrelations of the populations in the Akchadarya basin and the Lower Zarafshon valley.

Studying the interconnectedness of the populations residing in the area between the Syrdarya and Amudarya rivers in Central Asia is considered an important issue.

References:

1. Vinogradov, A.V. Neolithic Monuments of Khorezm. Moscow: Nauka, 1968. Issue 8, 170 pages.
2. Vinogradov, A.V. "Ancient Hunters and Fishermen of the Central Asian Interfluvium" // Transactions of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition. Moscow: Nauka, 1981. Issue XIII, 160 pages.
3. Tolstov, S.P. "Works of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition in 1954" // Soviet Oriental Studies. Moscow, 1955. No. 6, pp. 99-103. Itina, M.A. "New Sites of the Tazabagyab Culture (Works of 1956)" // Materials of the Khorezm Expedition. Moscow: Nauka, 1959. Issue I, pp. 52-150. Itina, M.A. "Excavations of the Kavat-3 Site in 1958" // Materials of the Khorezm Expedition. Moscow: Nauka, 1963. Issue 6, pp. 103-106. Itina, M.A. "Excavations of the Tazabagyab Culture Site in 1957" // Materials of the Khorezm Expedition. Moscow: Nauka, 1960. No. 6, pp. 99-103. Itina, M.A. "Excavations of the Tazabagyab Culture Burial Ground Kokcha-3" // Materials of the Khorezm Expedition. Moscow, 1961. Issue 5, pp. 3-96.
4. Itina, M.A. "Excavations on the Akchadarya" // Archaeological Discoveries 1976. Moscow: Nauka, 1977, p. 527. Itina, M.A. "Monuments of the Neolithic and Bronze Ages" // Antiquities of Southern Khorezm // Transactions of the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition. Moscow: Nauka, Volume XVI, pp. 72-79.

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5. Askarov, A. "The Zaman-Baba Culture in the Lower Zeravshan" // News of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. Tashkent: Fan, 1962. No. 1, pp. 59-65.
Askarov, A. Scenes from the Primitive History of Bukhara. Tashkent: Fan, 1973, pp. 15-21.
6. Askarov, A. "Excavations of the Bronze Age Burial Ground in Muminabad" // Materials of the Khorezm Expedition. Tashkent: Fan, 1969. Issue 8, pp. 56-62.

